

A Study of Stress Management and Social Maturity among Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

The present study examines the relationship between stress management and social maturity among adolescents. Adolescence is a critical developmental period marked by rapid physical, emotional, and social transitions. Effective stress management during this phase fosters resilience, while social maturity supports responsible and adaptive behavior. The sample comprised 200 adolescents (100 boys and 100 girls) drawn from government and private senior secondary schools in Mohali. Standardized tools the Stress Management Scale (Kaushik & Arora Charpe, 2011) and the Social Maturity Scale (Shrivastava, 1998, adapted) were used for data collection. Data was analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-tests. Results indicated no significant gender differences in stress management or social maturity. However, government school students exhibited higher stress management, whereas private school students displayed greater social maturity. No significant relationship was found between stress management and social maturity. The findings highlight the role of contextual factors in adolescent development and call for targeted educational interventions.

Keywords: Stress Management, Social Maturity, Adolescents, Senior Secondary School Students, Coping Strategies

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence, spanning from ages 13 to 21, is a transitional period marked by rapid biological, emotional, and social changes. Stress during this stage arises from academic pressures, family expectations, peer influences, and identity struggles. Poor stress management can lead to maladaptive behaviors, while effective management fosters resilience and well-being (Lazarus, 1996; Selye, 2011).

Simultaneously, social maturity the ability to engage in responsible, cooperative, and socially acceptable behavior plays a vital role in adolescent adjustment. A socially mature individual can manage emotions, communicate effectively, and adapt to changing social demands (Good, 1959; Shrivastava, 1998). This study examines how stress management relates to social maturity among adolescents.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. STUDIES RELATED TO STRESS MANAGEMENT

Musson and Loomis (2025) examined the impact of teacher burnout and supervision on the student-teacher relationship in the domains of closeness and conflict among a sample of early childhood educators (teachers). The study found that for closeness, students with a racial/ethnic match to their teachers were reported as having more closeness in their relationships ($p = 0.003$), though results related to conflict were insignificant. Higher teacher burnout was related to lower satisfaction with day-to-day tasks and work-related stress, and less frequent supervision. Results indicated that satisfaction with task supervision did not predict the intercept for closeness ($p = 0.234$) or conflict ($p = 0.418$). Similarly, satisfaction with stress-related supervision did not predict the intercept for student-teacher conflict ($p = 0.350$) or conflict ($p = 0.598$). Further, there was no moderation between supervision and stress, suggesting that satisfaction with task or stress-related supervision did not buffer the influence of burnout on student-teacher relationships.

Sethi (2023) examined the relationship between *Emotional Intelligence and Academic Stress among undergraduate college students*. 300 undergraduate students between the age group of 18-24 (150 boys and 150 girls) from the colleges of Balasore locality were selected randomly for the purpose. To evaluate Emotional Intelligence and Academic Stress, Shutte's Emotional Intelligence Test (SSREIT), and Students' Academic Stress Scale (SASS) of B. Rao (2008) was used respectively. For the analysis of obtained data, Pearson correlation and t-tests were employed. The result indicates that there is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic stress. Similarly, the result of t-test shows that there is no statistically significant difference in emotional intelligence with respect to gender. Further, there were no statistically significant differences in academic stress with respect to gender.

Kumar and Bawthra (2020) found that the stress mainly comes from academic tests, and career exploration. Such stress may usually cause psychological, physical, and behavioral problems. This study finds the causes of stress among youth and management strategies to overcome the stress.

2. STUDIES RELATED TO SOCIAL MATURITY

Umamaheswari and Karthikeyan (2024) conducted a study to find out social maturity among higher secondary students in relation to their academic achievement. The study involved Normative Survey Method in which 950 higher secondary school students from Government, Government Aided, and Private schools in Dharmapuri district were selected through random sampling technique. The results of the study revealed that the social maturity and academic achievement of higher secondary students was moderate. The results also revealed that there is significant positive correlation between social maturity and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Shanmuganathi (2020) conducted a study to find out *the level of Social Maturity among B.Ed. Student- Teachers* in the College of Education. This study involves to Normative Survey Method. The size of the sample in the study was 200 students- teachers who were selected through the Random Sampling Technique. The Major findings of the study were i) The level of Social Maturity among B.Ed. Student- Teachers in Colleges of Education are average. ii) Both Male and Female B.Ed. Student – teachers are having a similar level of Social Maturity. iii) Both Rural and urban B.Ed. Student – teachers are having a similar level of Social Maturity and iv) Both Arts and Science B.Ed. Student – teachers are having a similar level of Social Maturity.

Purohit (2020) examined *the social maturity among college students*. It also aimed to check social maturity with reference to gender and faculty. A Comprehensive for Social Maturity (ACSSM) prepared by Dr. Roma Pal (1986) was used. The sample constituted total 120 college students out of which 60 were from boys students (20 students of arts, 20 students of commerce and 20 students of science faculty) and 60 from girls students (20 students of arts, 20 students of commerce and 20 students of science faculty). The data was collected from Banaskantha District. The result showed that, there is significant difference in the mean score of social maturity among the boys and girls college students. Therefore, it could be said that, the girls college students group is having high social maturity than boys college students group. There is no significant difference in the mean score of social maturity among the college students of arts, commerce and science faculty, & 3. There is no significant difference in the interactive effect of the mean scores of social maturities with regards to the gender and faculty.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study and compare stress management among adolescent boys and girls.
- To study and compare stress management among government and private school adolescents.
- To study and compare social maturity among adolescent boys and girls.
- To study and compare social maturity among government and private school adolescents.
- To study stress management in relation to social maturity among adolescents.

HYPOTHESES

- There will be no significant difference in stress management among boys and girls.
- There will be no significant difference in stress management among government and private school adolescents.
- There will be no significant difference in social maturity among boys and girls.
- There will be no significant difference in social maturity among government and private school adolescents.

- There will be no significant relationship between stress management and social maturity.

METHODOLOGY

Design:

The present investigation employed a descriptive survey method as suggested by Best and Kahn (2008). This design was considered appropriate for studying the existing status of stress management and social maturity among adolescents without manipulating variables.

Sample:

The sample of the study consisted of 200 adolescents drawn from senior secondary schools of Mohali. It included 100 boys and 100 girls with equal representation from government and private institutions, ensuring gender and school type balance.

Tools used:

1. Stress Management Scale by Kaushik and Arora Charpe (2011).
2. Social Maturity Scale by Shrivastava (1998, adapted version).

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

The responses obtained were scored according to the respective manuals. Data analysis involved computing mean and standard deviation to study the general trends. The t-test was applied to examine differences across gender and school type.

RESULTS

The analysis of data was carried out in relation to the hypotheses formulated for the study. The results are presented with corresponding tables and interpretations.

Hypothesis 1: There will be no significant difference in stress management among boys and girls.

Table 1: Mean, SD, and t ratio for Stress Management among adolescent Boys (N =100) and Girls (N=100) school students.

Stress management	Boy/girl	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of significance
	Boys	100	130.1000	5.448	.470	Not significant
	Girls	100	129.7000	6.529		

The t-value for stress management of adolescent boys and girls is 0.470. This clearly indicates that there is no significant difference in stress management among adolescent boys and girls, although both the genders are good at managing their stress levels. Therefore hypothesis 1 stating, “There is no significant difference in stress management among adolescent boys and girls” is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There will be no significant difference in stress management among government and private school adolescents.

Table 2: Mean, SD, t-ratio for Stress Management among adolescent Government (N=100) and Private (N=100) school students.

Stress management	Government /private	N	Mean	SD	T	Level of significance
	Government	100	131.0000	4.798	2.630	Significant at 0.01
	Private	100	129.9000	6.850		

The findings revealed that there is significant difference in stress management among adolescent students studying in government and private schools as the t- value 2.630 was found significant at 0.01 level. Although both the government and private school students are good at managing their stress levels, government school students are better at managing their stress as compared to the private school students.

Therefore hypothesis 2 stating, “There will be no significant difference in stress management among adolescent students studying in government and private schools” is rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There will be no significant difference in social maturity among adolescent boys and girls.

Table 3: Mean, SD, t ratio for Social Maturity among adolescent Boys (N=100) and Girls (N= 100).

Social maturity	Boys/girls	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of significance
	Boys	100	52.7900	3.947	.2342	Not significant
	Girls	100	54.0900	3.903		

The t-value for social maturity of adolescent boys and girls is 0.2342. This indicates that There is no significant difference in social maturity among adolescent boys and girls.

Therefore hypothesis 3 stating, “There will be no significant difference in social maturity among adolescent boys and girls” is accepted.

Hypothesis 4: There will be no significant difference in social maturity among adolescent students studying in government and private schools.

Table 4: Mean, SD, t ratio for social maturity among adolescents Government (N=100) and Private (N=100) school students.

Social maturity	Government / private	N	Mean	SD	T	Level of significance
	Government	100	52.6500	3.497	2.955	At 0.01 level
	Private	100	54.2300	4.263		

The t-value for social maturity of government and private school adolescents is 2.955. This indicates that there is significant difference in social maturity among adolescents studying in government and private schools as t-ratio was found to be significant at 0.01 level.

Therefore hypothesis 4 stating “There will be no significant difference in social maturity among adolescent students studying in government and private schools” is rejected.

Hypothesis 5: There will be no significant difference in stress management among adolescents in relation to social maturity.

Table 5: Mean, SD, t ratio for Stress Management due to low and high scores of Social Maturity.

Stress management	Social maturity	N	Mean	SD	t	Level of significance
	High	54	129.7963	6.159	.756	Not significant
	Low	54	130.5926	4.684		

The results indicate that there exists no significant difference in stress management among adolescents in relation to social maturity as t- ratio 0.756, which was found to be

insignificant. It shows that stress management among adolescents with high and low social maturity levels is almost same.

Therefore, hypothesis 5 stating, “There will be no significant difference in stress management among adolescents in relation to social maturity” is accepted.

DISCUSSION

The results suggest that stress management and social maturity are influenced more by school context than by gender. Government school students displayed stronger stress management, perhaps due to lower academic pressures, while private school students demonstrated higher social maturity, likely owing to greater exposure to structured activities and diverse interactions.

Interestingly, the absence of a significant relationship between stress management and social maturity indicates that these two developmental constructs may function independently. This finding diverges from some earlier studies (Santrock, 2004; Alam, 2016), which highlight a stronger connection, suggesting that cultural and contextual differences play a role in shaping adolescent development.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that although both stress management and social maturity are essential to adolescent well-being, they may not necessarily be interrelated. School context exerts a stronger influence than gender in shaping these attributes. Strengthening coping strategies and fostering social maturity should remain educational priorities.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings underscore the importance of embedding stress management training and social skills development into the school curriculum. Teachers and parents should collaborate to create supportive environments that nurture resilience and responsible behavior. Enhanced counseling services and active participation in co-curricular activities can further promote both stress management and social maturity among adolescents.

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